

**UNIVERSITY OF LAY-ADVENTISTS OF KIGALI
(UNILAK)**

FACULTY OF LAW

**AN ANALYSIS OF THE LEGAL AND
INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK
FOR THE DOMESTICATION OF
INTERNATIONAL CRIMES UNDER
THE LIBERIAN LAW**

The Dissertation is submitted to the faculty of law for
partial fulfillment of the Academic requirements for
the award of bachelor's degree in law (L.L.B)

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Nyanza, April 2026

DECLARATION

I, Jess P. Walker, declare that this dissertation bearing the title “*An Analysis of the Legal and Institutional Framework for the Domestication of International Crimes under Liberian Law*” is entirely a product of my own research and analysis, and had not been submitted in fulfillment of the requirements of a degree purpose or for any academic purpose towards any higher institution of learning. Where any other individual work has been used, references have been provided in footnotes and bibliography.

Signature:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Jess P. Walker', written in a cursive style.

Date: 04/03/2026

DEDICATION

To the Almighty God;

To my Parents;

To my entire Family;

To my friends and Colleagues.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am deeply grateful to the Almighty God for granting me the knowledge and strength to have successfully completed this academic research.

I would also love to appreciate my parents and family **Mr. Joseph G. Walker, Mrs. Aletha Walker, Mr. Emmanuel Paye** and to my beloved aunty **Wlehdee Tweh** for their supports and guidance throughout this academic journey.

My gratitude also goes to the **University of Lay-Adventist of Kigali (UNILAK)** for providing the academic environments and opportunities to learn and undertake this research as part of a major requirement for the award of Bachelor of Law degree (LLB).

Finally, I would love to express a special thanks and appreciation to my supervisor **Mr. MUGISHA Cedric** for his guidance, constructive feedbacks and continuous supports throughout this research. His encouragement, supports and guidance contributed immensely to the success of this work and my LLB academic journey.

And also, to my colleagues, friends, and the entire class of March 2023, I am so grateful for the supports and love.

May God bless you all.

Jess P. WALKER

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ACHPR: African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights

Art: Article

BTI: Bertelsmann Stiftung Transformation Index

CPA: Comprehensive Peace Agreement

DRC: Democratic Republic of the Congo

ECC: Extraordinary Criminal Court

ICC: International Criminal Court

ICCPR: International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights

ICJ: International Court of Justice

ICTR: International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda

ICTY: International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia

IHL: International Humanitarian Law

IHRL: International Human Rights Law

LNP: Liberia National Police

MOJ: Ministry of Justice

P: Page

PGA: Parliamentarians for Global Action

SCSL: Special Court for Sierra Leone

SGBV: Sexual and Gender-Based Violence

TRC: Truth and Reconciliation Commission

UN: United Nations

ABSTRACT

International Criminal Law gives States the primary responsibility to prosecute the core international crimes in their domestic jurisdiction. Eventhough, the applicability of international criminal law in national jurisdictions still remains a complex issue, given the wide ranges of legal, political and institutional challenges. It is enshrined in preamble six and ten of the Rome Statute of the International criminal court that it is the duty of States to exercise its criminal jurisdiction over those responsible for international crimes, and that the court shall complement national jurisdictions.

The absence of international crimes in domestic law renders a country to be either unable or unwilling. This is the case of Liberia. The West African Nation civil conflict began in 1989 and lasted until 2003. It has been over twenty-one years since the conflict ended, but there is still no accountability. The possibilities of moving from impunity to this accountability still remains uncertain. And one key factor that continue to play in this quest is the lack of international crimes into the Country's domestic criminal frame work.

In the aftermath of the Liberia civil war, there were intentions to bring alleged perpetrators of War crimes and Crimes against humanity committed from 1989-2003 to the altar of justice. The Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Liberia was established to investigate the cause of the conflict and also make possible recommendations for justice. In 2009, one of the many recommendations made by the TRC, was to establish an extraordinary Criminal court, which shall posses a hybrid jurisdiction. Despite many efforts, the Court has not been established.

Liberia as a county on whose territory war crimes and crimes against humanity were committed until now, lacks jurisdiction to prosecute international crimes. The Liberia criminal law framework does not recognize war crimes, crimes against humanity, Genocide and Crime of Aggression. The applicability of international criminal law in Liberia remains connected with challenges. Legal Challenges like structure deficiencies in domestic laws, and other range of institutional obstacles. It is within this context that this research examines the challenges surrounding the domestication of international crimes in Liberia. It identified key legal and institutional gaps that hinders effective implementation. Using doctrinal and comparative approach, the study highlights several key issues, and propose targeted reforms.

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GENERAL INTRODUCTION

Liberia has become a typical example of an African State facing significant challenges within its Judicial system. Even though, the Liberia's civil war is officially over, war criminals are free, but the possibilities of moving from impunity to accountability in Liberia post-war still remains uncertain. One key factor that continue to play in the quest for accountability from the nation fourteen years of civil atrocities, is the lack of international crimes into its criminal frame work, in order to prosecute serious violation of international law domestically.

This research is concern with the Analysis of the legal and institutional framework for the domestication of international crimes under the Liberia law.

1. Background of the study

Liberia like many other African nations have experienced the wrath of civil conflict for many years. The west African nation was stricken by fourteen (14) consecutive years of civil war which claim the lives of at least half a million people, many of whom are said to be children, and innocent women. ¹

With the terrifying history and political instability, the nation has faced an immense challenge in prosecuting and addressing issues of accountability for serious violations of international law, especially during its civil conflict from 1989-2003. ²Atrocities including war crimes, crimes against humanity and other human rights violations till date are not accountable for, and have sparked calls for justice domestically and even internationally. Integrating local traditions with international legal frameworks poses significant challenges for post-conflict nations. International Law plays a crucial role in shaping the diplomatic, economic, and legal frameworks of nations. In Liberia, a country with a unique founding history and a prolonged period of civil unrest, the practice of international law has not been instrumental in navigating issues of post-conflict recovery.³

¹ A. J. Kuperman, "*Liberia: How Diplomacy Helped End a 13-Year Civil War*", Institute for National Security Studies, 2004, p. 10.

² K. Ballah, "*The History of the Civil War in Liberia*" International Journal of Political Science and governance, 2025,p.98

³ M.N Williams, "*The Practice of International Law in Liberia*", Beijing Law Review, 16, 273-289, 2025, P.12.

The first Liberia civil war lasted from the end of 1989 until the middle of 1997; the nation was devastated by a prolonged civil war fought among rival warlords who also represented ethnic (or "tribal") resentments. The origins of the war lay in a military mutiny in 1980 that ushered in nine years of brutal rule by the dictator Samuel Doe, Liberia's former president.

On Christmas Eve 1989 a member of the Americo-Liberian ruling class, Charles Taylor, invaded Liberia with a guerrilla army that within nine months had reached the capital, Monrovia. A splinter faction seized Doe and executed him and all, but one member of his cabinet. Despite the overthrow of Doe, the rival factions were unable to reach an agreement on a new government despite the intervention of a West African peace-keeping force.⁴

Between 1989 and 2003, civil war consumed the small West African nation of Liberia, resulting in the estimated deaths of 150,000 to 250,000 men, women and children, and the displacement of over half the country's population.⁵

On August 18, 2003, Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA) was signed, bringing an end to the 14-year conflict in which some sources estimate 250,000 people had lost their lives. The gross human rights violations committed during the conflicts included: massive killing of civilians, torture, widespread rape and sexual violence, forcible recruitment of children as soldiers, extortion, looting of the national economy, and the destruction of cultural property. The Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA) created a framework for a transitional government; called for political and economic reforms; and set out procedures for demobilization. The signatories to the CPA called for the establishment of a Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and envisioned that the TRC would provide a forum that would address issues of impunity.⁶ In lines with its mandates, Article 4 Section 4 of the Act Establishing the Truth and Reconciliation Commission highlights that the TRC Investigate gross human rights violations and violations of international humanitarian law as well as abuses that occurred, during the Liberian civil war⁷

⁴ EBSCO, "The Liberian civil war I: 1989-1997, available at www.ebsco.com/research-starters/military-history-and-science/liberian-civil-war-i-1989-1997, accessed January 20th, 2026.

⁵ Center for Justice and Accountability, "Liberia civil war part I, available at www.cja.org/where-we-work/liberia/#: accessed January 20th, 2026.

⁶ Center for Justice and Accountability, "Liberia Civil war part II, available at <https://cja.org/where-we-work/liberia/> accessed January 21, 2026

⁷ Act Establishing the Truth and Reconciliation Commission, 2005, Art. 4 Sec. 4.

In 2009, the TRC submitted a final report that identified serious violations of international law and human rights abuses committed by all sides of the armed conflict.⁸

To address these crimes, the TRC recommended the establishment of an Extraordinary Criminal Court for Liberia, an internationalized domestic criminal court with the power to prosecute alleged perpetrators of atrocity crimes, including war crimes, crimes against humanity, and gross violations of human rights, as well as a limited number of domestic and economic crimes.⁹ Political obstacles have often hinder the implementation of international legal norms.

Despite the many recommendations that was made by the TRC, there is still lack of accountability and gaps in the implementation of international laws in Liberia. With the growing development of international criminal law and the nation participation in several key international instruments, there is still a critical issue with the translation of this obligation into effective domestic criminal legislation. While the Rome Statute established standards for accountability, their effectiveness still depends on national implementation. In Liberia, there is still a question regarding the extent to which international crimes have been adequately incorporated into domestic law and whether the existent legal mechanism sufficiently reflect international standards. This gap between international commitment and domestic enforcement highlights the need for a closer examination of Liberia legal framework. Understanding these limitations of the domestication of international crimes is essential for accessing national accountability and strengthening the rule of law. Based on this, this research will systematically address examine whether international crimes are properly incorporated into Liberia domestic framework.

⁸ TRC, *“Preliminary findings and determinations Reports”*, Volume 1, 2009, P. 6.

⁹ *Ibid.*

2. Problem Statement

Liberia is a member of many international treaties and has ratified many key legal instruments like the Rome statute of the international criminal court of 1998, ratified in 2004¹⁰, the Geneva conventions of 1949 and its Additional protocols of 1977 and is a party to several human rights conventions. Despite these ratifications, Liberia is yet to domesticate international crimes such as war crimes, Genocide, crimes against humanity, and Aggression. The current Liberian criminal law, particularly the Penal Law of 1978 and its amendments, lacks comprehensive provisions that define, criminalize, and provide procedural mechanisms for the prosecution of these grave offenses in accordance with international standards.

This legal gap possesses a significant barrier to justice and accountability, especially in the context of the atrocities committed during Liberia's civil conflicts. The Rome statute of 1998 which Liberia is a party to stipulates in paragraph six of its preamble that "Recalling that it is the duty of every State to exercise its criminal jurisdiction over those responsible for international crimes."¹¹ This paragraph emphasizes several key principles like serious crimes must not go unpunished, genocide, war crimes, crime against humanity are too grave to be ignored. And that countries are expected to investigate and prosecute these crimes themselves, which Liberia has not done. The penal law, and the Criminal Procedure law of Liberia does not define or criminalize crimes like war crimes, crimes against humanity, Genocide and Aggression.

According to Article 17(a) of the Rome statute of 1998, cases shall be deemed to be inadmissible before the ICC if the case is being investigated or prosecuted by a State which has jurisdiction over it, unless that the State is unwilling or unable genuinely to carry out the investigation or prosecution. ¹²The failure of Liberia to domesticate international crimes such as War crimes, and crimes against Humanity under its national criminal law framework renders the country legally and institutionally unable to genuinely carry out investigations and prosecutions, as defined under Article 17 of the Rome Statute.

¹⁰ ICC, "Liberia ratified the statute of the international Criminal court" available at <https://asp.icc-cpi.int/press-releases/press-releases-2004/liberia-ratifies-the-rome-statute-of-the-international-criminal-court> accessed 19 January 2026

¹¹ Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court of 1998, Preamble 10.

¹² *Id.*, Art. 17.

This provision is central to the principle of complementarity, which holds that the International Criminal Court (ICC) may only intervene when national jurisdictions are unwilling or unable to prosecute serious international crimes. As of now, Liberia's Penal Code does not incorporate the definitions, jurisdictional standards, or procedural mechanisms necessary to prosecute these crimes domestically.

In this context, the absence of domestication places Liberia in technical violation of the Rome Statute's expectation that States bear primary responsibility for the prosecution of international crimes. Thus, without comprehensive domestic legal reform, Liberia remains functionally and legally unable under Article 17(1)(a) and (b), reinforcing the case for either ICC intervention or urgent national legislation to align with international obligations.

3. Research questions

This research intends to answer the following questions:

- (i) How adequately has Liberia fulfilled its international legal obligations to domesticate and prosecute international crimes under its domestic criminal law framework?
- (ii) What are the main legal and institutional challenges affecting the domestication and prosecution of international crimes in Liberia?
- (iii) What reforms or mechanisms can be introduced to improve the domestication and enforcement of international crimes within Liberia's criminal justice system?

4. Research Objectives

4.1. General objectives

To critically examine the challenges hindering the effective domestication of international crimes into the Liberia criminal law framework and to provide a vital mechanism to enhance Liberia compliance with its legal international obligations.

4.2. Specific objectives

- (i) To critically analyze the legal and institutional gaps within the domestic legal and judicial framework of Liberia that hinder the effective domestication and prosecution of international crimes.

- (ii) To examine the implementation status and legal impact of the recommendations made by the Truth and Reconciliation Commission, particularly regarding the establishment of a war crimes court and related legal reforms.
- (iii) To comparatively analyze Liberia's legal approach to the domestication of international crimes with post-conflict experiences in Sierra Leone and Rwanda, focusing on how these countries integrated international crimes into their national legal systems.

5. Interest of the Study

The findings of this study are useful for educational purposes and even highlights the importance of legal reforms in promoting justice and accountability in Liberia. The study lies in understanding how the domestication of international crimes in Liberia can contribute to end impunity for past atrocities, strengthening the national legal system, and aligning Liberia's legal framework with international standards.

The study serves as a strategic tool to help lawmakers and even the Ministry of Justice understand what legal reforms are necessary to align Liberia's laws with international standards (e.g., Rome Statute implementation). The findings will also be useful for institutional reforms and can be used to facilitate the government's efforts to build a more accountable and transparent justice system, particularly in addressing impunity and preventing future atrocities.

6. Research Methodology

In order to address the legal issues raised in the problem of statements and fulfill the objectives of this study, many research techniques and methods have been used.

The documentary techniques which is paramount to this study was used for the collection of data and pieces of information through the reading of legal documents or framework relating to the topic. These documents include laws, journals, newspapers, text books, annual reports and articles written by renowned international organization observers and representatives operating in and around Liberia. The Research Methods are doctrinal and comparative. The doctrinal approach analyses relevant legal texts, principles and authorities governing the incorporation of international crimes into domestic law.

In addition, the research employs a comparative approach. This method enables a comparison of Liberia legal approach to the domestication of international crimes with other post war conflicts countries that have integrated and prosecuted international crimes into their national laws.

7. Scope of the Study

The scope of this study is limited in terms of domain, territorial application and temporal coverage. It specifically confined several legal frameworks governing the incorporation of international crimes into domestic law. It examines crimes recognize under international criminal law, such as Genocide, war crime, Crime against humanity and Crime of Aggression. It over all focuses on treaties, statutory elements, and legal principles that determines whether and how these crimes can be incorporated into Liberia legal system.

The territorial scope of this study is limited to Liberia. Although comparative references will be made for selected foreign jurisdiction for an analytical purpose, but the primary focus remains on Liberia and its ability to prosecute international crimes within its territory.

Finally, the study covers the period from the nation 1986 constitution till present, including its 1978 penal law and its subsequent amendment or subtitles. References are also made to the civil conflict period from 1989-2003 where relevant in order to understand the application of international crimes.

8. Structural of the Study

The study comprises a general introduction along with three substantive chapters and a general conclusion. Chapter one deals with the definition of key terms and general consideration on the domestication of international crimes. Chapter two focused on the legal and institutional challenges in domesticating international crimes into Liberia criminal legal framework. And finally, chapter three focused on proposed Mechanism for overcoming the Legal and institutional challenges to the domestication of international crimes in Liberia.

CHAPTER ONE: CONCEPTUAL AND GENERAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK ON THE DOMESTICATION OF INTERNATIONAL CRIMES

This Chapter focuses on the conceptual frameworks, ideas and opinions from different authors relating to the research topic. It also examines the general consideration on domesticating international crimes.

1.1. Conceptual framework

This section examines the conceptual legal frameworks governing the domestication of international crimes. It provides an analytical view on these key concepts and explain how they align with the domestication of international crimes.

1.1.1 International crimes

Any examination of domestication requires clarity as to what qualify as an international crime, since the scope of incorporation also depends on how such crimes are define at the international level. International crimes are crimes which violate or threaten the fundamental values or interests protected by international law and which are of concern to the international community as a whole. These crimes are of most serious concern to the international community and they threaten the peace, security and well-being of the world.¹³

Today, these core international crimes as recognized by article 5 of the Rome Statute of the international criminal court are Genocide, War Crimes, Crimes Against Humanity and Crime of Aggression. ¹⁴The contemporary legal definition of genocide is specified under Article 6 of the Rome Statute which reflects the 1948 Genocide convention. It involves acts committed with the intent to destroy, in whole or in part, a national, ethnical, racial, or religious group. ¹⁵ While its elements are specified in international law, domestic incorporation requires recognizing the collective and intentional dimension of group destruction.

Also defined by the Rome Statute, War Crimes are serious violations of the laws and customs applicable in armed conflict, encompassing both international and non-international conflicts.

¹⁶These violations include grave breaches of the Geneva Conventions and other serious violations

¹³ M. Cedric, *International criminal law*, course notes, UNILAK, Faculty of Law, 2026, p. 58.

¹⁴ Rome Statute *supra* note 11, art. 5

¹⁵ *Id.*, art. 6.

¹⁶ Customary IHL Rules 156.

of the laws and customs of war. The Rome Statute outlines specific acts considered war crimes, such as the use of child soldiers, attacks against civilians and civilians objects, torture, and the destruction of cultural property.¹⁷

The contemporary legal definition of Crime Against humanity is also codified in Article 7 of the Rome Statute which provides that acts like murder, extermination, enslavement, deportation, imprisonment, torture, rape, and persecution, when committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian population constitute a Crime Against humanity.¹⁸

The definition of Crime Against humanity which is codified under Article 8 of the Rome Statute following the Kamapala amendment in adopted in 2010,¹⁹ defines the crime as an act that involves the planning, preparation, initiation, or execution of an act of aggression by a person in a position to effectively control or direct a state's political or military action.

The legal construction of these international crimes is normative which must be reflected in domestic legislation and accordingly, by defining them at this level is necessary in order to assess whether Liberia's existing criminal law framework captured these internationally recognize offences.

1.1.2 Domestication of international Crimes

The concept of international criminal justice ultimately depends not on international tribunals but also on the willingness and ability of States to prosecute. The domestication of international crimes is the process by which States incorporate or transpose the substantive provisions of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (ICC) and related international criminal law into their domestic legal systems. Occur via codification, transformation of treaty norms into domestic legislation, or adaptation to national constitutional requirements.²⁰ it is not merely by ratification of a treaty, but it is the transformation of treaty obligation into enforceable national legislation.

¹⁷ Rome Statute *supra* note 11, Art. 8.

¹⁸ *Id.*, Art. 7.

¹⁹ X "Campaign for the ratification and implementation of the Kampala amendment of the Crime Against human, available at <https://crimeofaggression.info/2013/01/depositary-notification-adoption-of-the-amendments-on-the-crime-of-aggression-2010/> accessed March 1, 2026

²⁰ J. Florian, et al (eds), *Domesticating International Criminal Law; Reflections on the Italian and German Experiences* 1st ed, Routledge, 2023, P. 3.

For Liberia, the question is not whether it has ratified the Rome Statute but whether its criminal law framework substantively criminalize international crimes.

1.1.3 Principle of Legality

The principle of legality is central to any discussion on the domestication of international crimes, as it defines the constitutional and criminal limits within which State may enact and apply criminal legislation. The principle of legality *nullum crimen, nulla poena sine lege* states that no one can be punished for a conduct without it being provided by law as a punishable offense.²¹ It is recognized under Article 22 of the Rome Statute which prohibits retroactive criminal law. While international law may recognize conduct as criminal, domestic courts may be constitutionally barred from prosecuting it if no enabling legislation existed at the relevant time. Especially in the case of Liberia where international crimes committed during the civil conflict were not expressly codified in domestic law at the time of their commission.

1.1.4 Complementarity

This principle represents the idea that states, rather than the International Criminal Court (ICC), will have priority in proceeding with cases within their jurisdiction.²² It means that National courts will continue to have priority in investigating and prosecuting crimes committed within their jurisdictions, but the International Criminal Court will act when national courts are 'unable or unwilling' to perform their tasks.²³ For Liberia, Complementarity raises the question that if international crimes committed during civil conflict are not adequately incorporated into domestic law, and if prosecutions are not undertaken, could it trigger ICC admissibility under the “unable or unwilling” standard. Thus, the answer always lies whether Liberia criminal law framework demonstrate unwillingness and inability.

²¹ N. Lutfiu et al., “*The Principle of Legality in International Criminal Law*”, Journal of posthumanism, 2025, p. 3.

²² R Cryer *et.al.*, “*An introduction to International Criminal Law and Procedure*”, 2nd Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2007, p.127.

²³ L. Carter “*The Principle of Complementarity and the International Criminal Court: The Role of Ne Bis in Idem*”, McGeorge School of Law Scholarly Article, 2010, p.4.

1.2 General legal Context of the Domesticating of International Crimes

The notion of domesticating international crimes which involves incorporating international crimes into domestic laws, is an essential step for ensuring. ²⁴ This section provides a general overview of the legal framework governing the domestication of international crimes, with particular reference to the evolution of the practice of international criminal law in domestic and hybrid tribunals, and the obligations arising under the Rome Statute.

The domestication of international crime is deeply rooted in the modern development of international criminal law which emerged from the need to hold individuals accountable for atrocities that threaten the peace and security of the world. Traditionally, international law did not impose criminal liability on individuals, however, the turning point of this began with the establishment of the Nuremberg and Tokyo tribunals in 1945 and 1946 after the second world war. It was emphasized by the Nuremberg trial by urging that ‘Crimes against international law are committed by men, not by abstract entities, and only by punishing individuals who commit such crimes can the provision of international law be enforced’²⁵.

The development of international criminal law was further strengthened through international treaties that require states to criminalize certain acts under their domestic legal systems. One of the earliest examples is the convention on the prevention and punishment of genocide. Article 5 obligates states to prevent and punish genocide and to enact the necessary legislation to give effect to the Convention.²⁶ Similarly, the Geneva convention also requires states to prosecute individuals responsible for grave violation of international humanitarian law.²⁷

Another modern framework for the domestication of international crime is linked to the establishment of the Rome Statute of the international criminal court. A key feature of the Rome Statute is its principle of complementarity, which provides that the ICC is not intended to replace national criminal jurisdictions. Instead, that the court would only exercise its jurisdiction where the State Party of which the accused is a national is unable or unwilling to prosecute. This principle

²⁴ X International Law meaning and implementation, retrieved at “<https://citylawtutors.co.uk/law-journal/international-law-meaning-and-implementation-an-analysis>” accessed March 1 2026

²⁵ M Cedric, *supra* note 13, p. 12.

²⁶ Convention on the prevention and punishment of genocide of 1948, Art. 5.

²⁷ Fourth Geneva Convention of 1949, Art. 146.

is now regarded as an important part of the role of the International Court systems.²⁸ The principle is not only a concession of justice to sovereignty, but the basis of a system of justice with domestic responsibility as a starting point.²⁹

Through these developments, some States have defined and provide for international crimes in their national criminal law. Many of whom who are parties to treaties like the ICC Statute copy the definition of most of the crimes found in the document into their national law.³⁰ In addition to this, a growing number of States have also set up specialized investigating units and dedicated departments within their prosecution offices to deal with the complexities of such investigations and prosecution of core international crimes.³¹

In international criminal law, domestication is not merely administrative compliance, it is the mechanism through which states assume responsibility for the investigation and prosecution of international crimes.

This section therefore examines, first, the international legal obligation requiring implementation, second, the theories governing the reception of international law (monism and dualism) that determine how international norms enter into domestic systems, and third, the complementarity regime under the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, which reinforces domestic prosecutorial responsibility.

1.2.1 International Obligation to Implement International Criminal Law

With the adoption of the Rome Statute in 1998, the vast majority of States have called for a global Criminal justice system determined to put an end to impunity for the perpetrators of international crimes. Within this system, the international Criminal Court play just a complementary role. Adequate legislation at the States' level that reflects the substantive provisions of the Rome Statute is a precondition for compliance. And indeed, over the past 20 years, many States have adopted specific legislation to incorporate international criminal law into their domestic legal systems. It

²⁸ D. Byron, "*International Conference on the Legacy of the ICTR*" Madibeng Council of Chambers University of Johannesburg, 2013, p. 2.

²⁹ B. E. Mayans et al., "*Balancing the International and the Domestic Sanction under the ICC principle of complementarity*," journal of international criminal justice volume 18, 2020, p.5.

³⁰ W. N. Ferdinandusse, *Direct Application of International Law in National Courts*, the Hague, T.M.C Asser Press, 2006, p. 7.

³¹ J.Florian, *supra* note, 20, p. 2.

is through the process of incorporation, that a state is able to implement the international obligations to its domestic or municipal legal system.

The duty of States to implement international criminal law domestically also derives from the foundational *principle of pacta sunt servanda*, codified under Article 26 of the Vienna Convention on the law of treaties. This principle requires treaties in force to be performed in good faith. And where a State has ratified treaties imposing an obligation to prosecute and incorporate the repression of international crimes, good faith entails the adoption of legislation and institutional measures capable giving practical effect to those obligations.³² The concept of *pacta sunt servanda* is very important in the enforcement of international criminal law because it ensures the efficiency of the implementation of international treaties such as the Rome Statute of 1998. States are required to actively collaborate with the ICC in investigating and prosecuting cases of international crimes.³³

The *pacta sunt servanda* principle are also actualized through the implementation of the Rome Statute. Specifically, through incorporating and prosecuting the crime of Genocide, war crimes, and crimes against humanity domestically. Accordingly, Article 27 of the Vienna convention further reinforces this duty by prohibiting States from invoking internal law as justification for non-compliance.

The primary source of international criminal law are enshrined in Article 38 of the statute of the International court of justice (ICJ), which provides that the Court, whose function is to decide in accordance with international law such disputes as are submitted to it, shall apply: a. international conventions, whether general or particular, establishing rules expressly recognized by the contesting states ; b. international custom, as evidence of a general practice accepted as law; c. the general principles of law recognized by civilized nations ; d. subject to the provisions of Article 59, judicial decisions and the teachings of the most highly qualified publicists of the various nations, as subsidiary means for the determination of rules of law.³⁴ Treaties, customary

³² Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties of 1969, Art. 26.

³³ R Widiyantoro & J Setiyono, “*Analysis of the Principles of the Sunt Servanda Pacta in International Criminal Law Enforcement: Implementation and Challenges*”, Journal of Social Research, 2025, p.2.

³⁴ ICJ Statute of 1945, Art. 26.

international law, the general principle of law are typically the primary sources of international criminal law.

The implementation of international criminal laws also requires the implementation of these sources into national jurisdiction. And its major mechanism is by domesticating international laws.

Another duty of a state to implement treaty obligation through domestic legislation is enshrined in Article 146 of the fourth Geneva convention of 1949. It provides that “States must enact legislation to provide effective penal sanctions for persons committing grave breaches and must search for such persons and bring them before their own courts or hand them over for trial to another state”.³⁵ Such treaty obligations likewise reinforce the principle that states bear the responsibility to prosecute international crimes within their domestic jurisdictions.

The primary obligation of nations is to promote human rights; this extends to the duty to protect the citizens from grievous international crimes. Therefore, in performing this duty, the State must make considerations to prevent and curb the occurrence of these crimes provided under the Rome Statute in accordance with its applicable national criminal systems.³⁶

1.2.2 Theories governing the Reception of International law

While international law imposes a binding obligation upon States to implement international criminal law norms, the way in which such norms is acquire into domestic legal system is not uniform. whether international criminal norms become directly applicable upon ratification, or require legislative reforms depends on the theory of reception adopted by a state. It is therefore necessary to examine the doctrine of monism and dualism, which structure the interface between international and municipal laws.

1.2.2.1 Monism

The Interplay between international law and domestic law lies within the concept of two scholarly theories, one of them is Monism.³⁷ The Monism theory established that international law serves as a source of law that is incorporated into and superior to domestic law, not just as a legal framework to guide state-to-state relations in the international order. As a result, a treaty that has been legally

³⁵ Fourth Geneva Convention, *supra* note 27, art. 146.

³⁶ I. Akpotue “*The role of domestic court and international criminal court in investigating and prosecuting international crimes; the principle of complementarity*” SSRN Working paper, 2022, p. 10

³⁷ W. N. Ferdinandusse, *supra* note. 30, p. 130.

ratified or approved becomes part of a national legal system. The theory is based on the idea that international law is not separate from domestic law but rather operates within the same legal framework. As a result, international legal norms may have direct effect within the domestic legal system, allowing individuals to rely on them before national courts. In monist systems, courts are therefore able to interpret and apply international law alongside domestic legislation, provided that the international rule is sufficiently clear and precise.³⁸ It simply provides that international law can be applied and enforced into domestic court without the need of domestication. This doctrine is linked with the effort of international lawyers to ensure the primacy of international obligations over national ones, this being a paramount condition for the binding force of international law as a whole.³⁹

1.2.2.2 Dualism

Unless the monist theory, in the Dualist paradigm, there is a distinction between international legal duties that nations as sovereigns agree to acknowledge in their foreign interactions and domestic legal standards that bind the state and its citizens or subjects in internal relationships. As a result, international law can only have binding legal force at the national or municipal level if it is firstly domesticated.⁴⁰ The theory promised to set international law on its own feet, it is not part of internal law. It is separated, it is a legal order in itself and it cannot be adulterated by unilateral acts of municipal law. *pacta sunt servanda* is its main rule that rule is beyond the reach of any single state.

The dichotomy between Monism and dualism establishes a starting point for the analysis of the effects of international law in the national legal orders. It addresses one of the most fundamental questions whether international law is actually part of, and thus presumptively valid in, the national legal order. The distinction between both monism and dualism has direct implications for the domestication of international crimes. Whereas the dualist systems require treaty obligations to be transformed through national legislation before they can generate criminal liability. In the absence

³⁸ J. Starke, “*Monism and Dualism in the theory of International Law*” Oxford Academic, 1999, p.537-552.

³⁹ R. Kolb et al., “*Monism and Dualism*” Max Planck Encyclopedia of Comparative Constitutional Law, Oxford University press, 2020, p.4.

⁴⁰ S. Garg, “*Monist v.s Dualist theory of international law*”, International journal of legal science and innovation, volume 2, 2023, p.4.

of such legislative incorporation, international criminal norms remain unenforceable domestically, notwithstanding the state's international commitment.

Even though the two theories are the starting point for a highly complicated discourse that requires a thorough separation of theory and practice. Many instances of State practice can be explained both under monist and dualist theories. Others use monism and dualism as labels for a particular legal system, asserting that certain State are monists and others are dualist. And this often focusses on the direct application of international law.⁴¹

The theory adopted by a State therefore shapes the practical enforceability of international criminal norms within its domestic laws. Where legislative transformation is absent, question arises as regards to state capacity to prosecute international crimes. It is within this context that the principle of complementarity under the Rome Statute assume central importance.

1.2.3 The Complementarity Regime under the Rome Statute

The Complementarity principle is a fundamental principle under the Rome Statute which regulates the role of the ICC in relation to domestic courts. In this subsection the principle is examine primarily as jurisdictional admissibility rule under Article 17 and paragraph 10 of the Rome Statute. While it may also reflect the political compromise between States, its operation function is to determine when the ICC may exercise jurisdiction on the basis of unwillingness or inability. It is however through this admissibility framework that domestic implementation acquires practical significant.

This principle is provided in paragraph 10 of the Preamble of the ICC which states that the "International Criminal Court established under this Statute shall be complementary"⁴² and Article 1 of the Statute which provides that the court shall be complementary to national criminal jurisdiction.⁴³ The principle encourages states to build and strengthen their domestic judicial systems. National courts do have the primary responsibility to investigate and prosecute grave international crimes. The ICC only serve as a backup system.

⁴¹ W. N. Ferdinandusse, *supra* note. 30, p. 131.

⁴² Rome Statute, *supra* note 11, preamble 10.

⁴³ *Id.*, art.1.

The ICC Statute explicitly acknowledge the idea of decentralized administration of justice⁴⁴. In this light, the complementarity principle that is mentioned in Article 17 of the Statute provides that in line with paragraph 10 of the Preamble and Article 1, the Court shall determine that a case is inadmissible where the case is being investigated or prosecuted by a State which has jurisdiction over it, unless the State is unwilling or unable genuinely to carry out the investigation or prosecution. That the case has been investigated by a State which has jurisdiction over it and the State has decided not to prosecute the person concerned, unless the decision resulted from the unwillingness or inability of the State genuinely to prosecute. That the person concerned has already been tried for conduct which is the subject of the complaint, and a trial by the Court is not permitted under article 20, paragraph 3. And that the case is not of sufficient gravity to justify further action by the Court. ⁴⁵ The effect is that the ICC as a court only complement and supplement national jurisdiction when prosecuting international crimes. This means that unlike the ICTY, the ICTR, and other mixed internationalized criminal Tribunals, the ICC wields no primary jurisdiction over national courts. Instead, States are given the primary responsibility, or right, to prosecute such crimes.⁴⁶

Furthermore, in determining the unwillingness of a State to investigate and prosecute alleged perpetrators of international crimes, the ICC also takes into account three conditions, as specified under article 17(2) of its statute. First, the ICC shall consider whether the national proceedings intend to shield from the criminal responsibility. Second, the ICC shall examine if there is unjustifiable delay in proceedings that is inconsistent with the intent to bring a person to justice. Third, it shall consider whether the proceedings were not conducted independently, impartially or in manner consistent to bring the person to justice. The ability of states to fulfil these roles is significant for the effectiveness of the ICC in fighting` impunity.

Also, in determining the inability of a State, a State is considered unable where its Judicial system has collapsed, it lacks legal framework or it lacks capacity to prosecute. A skeletal definition enshrined under Article 17(3) of the ICC statute provides that “to determine inability in a particular case, the Court shall consider whether, due to a total or substantial collapse or unavailability of its

⁴⁴ G.Werle, “*Principles of international Criminal Law*”, the Hague, T.M.C Asser Press, 2005, p.74.

⁴⁵ Rome Statute, *supra* note 11, Art.17.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

national judicial system, the State is unable to obtain the accused or the necessary evidence and testimony or otherwise unable to carry out its proceedings.⁴⁷

In the context of Liberia, whether the country is unwilling or unable remains a complex question since the ICC has not made a formal determination. But however, analytically speaking, certain legislative and institutional gaps may raise concerns regarding Liberia capacity to fully satisfy the complementarity standards under Article 17 of the Rome Statute. The stronger argument is that the nation face both legal and structural inability with the absence of comprehensive implementing legislation and limited prosecutorial capacity to handle complex international crimes. This particularly leans towards inability since Liberia lacks the capacity to prosecute and also lacks legal framework.⁴⁸ While Liberia has ratified key international treaties and assumed obligations under them, the practical realization of these obligations depends on domestic legal and institutional capacity.

In order to interact actively with national courts, the ICC has embraced a policy that has come to be called positive complementarity. This principle is coined generally from the idea that the Court, and particularly the Chief Prosecutor, should work to engage national jurisdictions in prosecutions, using various methods to encourage states to prosecute cases domestically whenever possible. The ultimate goal of such a policy is to strengthen domestic capacity, which arguably will have a significant positive impact on prevention of future atrocities.⁴⁹

In summary, this principle of complementarity reinforces the need for states to incorporate international crimes into their domestic legal systems. And it is by doing so that national courts will remain the primary forum for prosecuting such crimes while the ICC functions as a court of last resort. It also operationalizes the duty of domestic implementation by conditioning international intervention upon national default.

⁴⁷ G. Mcneal, “*ICC Inability in light of the Dujail case*”, Paper, Pepperdine University, Rick J. Caruso School of Law, June 2007, p. 1.

⁴⁸ M, William, *supra* note 3, p.286

⁴⁹ K. A. Marshall, “*Prevention and Complementarity in the International Criminal Court: A Positive Approach*,” SSRN e-Library, 2019, p.22.

CHAPTER TWO: ANALYSIS OF CHALLENGES HINDERING THE DOMESTICATION OF INTERNATIONAL CRIMES UNDER THE LIBERIAN CRIMINAL LAW

This chapter examines the challenges affecting the effective domestication and prosecution of international crimes under the Liberian criminal law. Although Liberia has ratified a number of international instruments that impose obligations to prevent and prosecute serious international crimes, the implementation of these obligations at the domestic level remains limited.⁵⁰ This chapter first analyzes the constraints that have hindered Liberia's ability to fulfill its obligation under ratified treaties. It further highlights challenges arising within the national legal frameworks, examining both legal and institutional barriers that affect the domestication and effective prosecution of international crimes in Liberia.

2.1 Difficulties in fulfilling Liberia's International Legal Obligation to Prosecute International Crimes

This section purposefully examines the constraints hindering Liberia's ability to fulfill its international legal obligations by prosecution international crimes domestically.

2.1.1 Limited implementation of Obligations under Ratified Treaties

This subsection critically examines the limited implementation of obligations undertaken by Liberia pursuant to ratified treaties.

2.1.1.1 Constraints in implementing the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court in Liberia

The Rome Statute, the treaty that established the International Criminal Court, signed by Liberia on July 17, 1998,⁵¹ requires the nation to criminalize Genocide, Crimes against Humanity, and War crimes⁵². Yet, the country does not have an implementing legislation. The parliamentarians for Global Actions (PGA) Secretariat provided a draft bill on cooperation with the ICC to its Members in 2007. In 2013, Hon. Doe Sherrif, a parliamentarian for global action member, introduced a private member's bill implementing the substantial and cooperation

⁵⁰ X "The Advocates for Human Rights" available at https://www.theadvocatesforhumanrights.org/Res/chapter_14-recommendations_submitted_to_the_truth_and_reconciliation_commission_of_liberia accessed March 2 2026

⁵¹ ICC, "Liberia ratified the statute of the international Criminal court" available at <https://asp.icc-cpi.int/press-releases/press-releases-2004/liberia-ratifies-the-rome-statute-of-the-international-criminal-court> accessed March 2 2026

⁵² Rome Statute, *supra* note 11, art.1.

provisions of the ICC statute to the Senate of the Liberian parliament. But the bill was not discussed.⁵³ As a member of the Rome Statute, Liberia undertook a binding international legal obligations to cooperate with the International Criminal Court by adopting a national measure that will ensure its corporation and allows for domestic prosecution of international crimes.

Article 88 of the Rome Statute requires its members “States to ensure that there are procedures available under their national law for all of the forms of cooperation.”⁵⁴ Liberia difficulties in fulfilling its international obligation to prosecute international crimes can be attributed to a combination of institutional, and legal challenges. The country civil war significantly weakens some State institution, particularly the Judiciary, thereby undermining the country’s capacity to prosecute serious international crimes. The failure to implement the recommendation from the Truth and Reconciliation commission on the establishment of an extraordinary criminal court further demonstrates some challenges affecting Liberia to meet its international obligation.

It is obvious from the ICC’s purpose and structure that full cooperation of States parties is not only inherent in the Court but also essential to its proper functioning. The drafters of the Rome Statute envisioned a comprehensive system of international justice that is based first and foremost on the individual States fulfilling their obligations to investigate and prosecute international crimes.⁵⁵

Moreover, the ICC involvement has been limited by the principle of *non-retroactivity*. Meaning that the ICC can only prosecute individuals for crimes committed after the Statute entered into force on 1 July 2002 and that the acts must have been criminal at the time they were committed. Given that majority of the Liberian war took place before this period, this has been seen as one of the major backlashes for ICC intervention. Eventhough Preamble six of the Statute still requires State to exercise its criminal jurisdiction over those responsible for international crimes.⁵⁶

Consequently, the 1984 Convention Against Torture, a peremptory norm of customary international law required States to criminalize acts of torture, establish jurisdiction, and prosecute or extradite alleged perpetrators. This reflects a whole broader international duty to prevent

⁵³ Parliamentarian for Global action “Liberia and the Rome Statute” available at <https://www.pgaction.org/ilhr/rome-statute/liberia.html#>: accessed March 2nd 2026

⁵⁴ Rome statute *supra* note 11, art. 26.

⁵⁵ J. Jessica “*Legal Obligations of States and Organizations Under the Rome Statute*” War Crimes Memoranda 2015, p. 7.

⁵⁶ Rome Statute *supra* note 11, preamble 10.

impunity for serious violations of international human rights law, even when such acts are not part of widespread or systematic attacks as required under the Rome Statute.⁵⁷ Despite this, and irrespective of several calls to review and amend Liberia's national laws in order to ensure the domestication and prosecution of international crimes,⁵⁸ the obligation has been limited by both institutional weakness, and legacy from its civil conflict.

The obligation to integrate the Rome Statute into Liberia's domestic legal framework is a practical prerequisite for the exercise of national jurisdiction over international crimes. Where such legislative incorporation is absent, questions arise concerning the state's capacity to investigate and prosecute conduct falling within the Court's jurisdiction. It is within this context that the doctrine of unwillingness and inability under Article 17 of the Rome Statute assumes particular relevance.

2.1.1.2 Insufficient Domestic Enforcement of the Geneva Convention

Liberia acceded to the Geneva Conventions of 1949 in 1954 and its Additional Protocols in 1988 which together make up the body of international humanitarian law. These conventions require the prosecution of grave breaches, which include War crimes. Being a party to these foundational treaties of international humanitarian law brings Liberia to a broader trend of global acceptance of the Geneva Conventions, to prosecute gross violation of international criminal law.⁵⁹

In 2019, at the 70th Commemoration of the Geneva Convention in Liberia, the ICRC through its Deputy Regional Head of Delegation Valerie Auber insisted on the importance of a legislative process and encouraged the swift adoption of a bill to domesticate all IHL treaties in the nation. Despite the unflinching support to the domestication of the Geneva Conventions that was made by a few Liberian parliamentarians attending the event, the Bill is yet to be passed at the house of parliament.⁶⁰ There is still limited domestication of the grave breaches provisions of the Geneva convention into the Liberian criminal law. The Geneva convention require States to enact legislation to enact grave breaches such as willful killing, torture or inhumane treatment as war

⁵⁷ Convention Against Torture of 1984, Art.5.

⁵⁸ Amnesty International "International Criminal Court: Burundi and Liberia - Ratification is an important commitment towards ending impunity, Relief web, available at <https://reliefweb.int/report/burundi/international-criminal-court-burundi-and-liberia-ratification-important-commitment> accessed March 3rd 2026

⁵⁹ International Committee of the Red Cross, "*State Party to the following international humanitarian law and other treaties*", ICRC, 2026, p.3.

⁶⁰O. Bestman, "*Liberia Recommits to Geneva Conventions*" Liberia National Red Cross Society media center, 2019.

crimes, however Liberia criminal law does not criminalize these offences as war crimes, making it difficult for domestic courts to prosecute such violation as an act which constitute an international offence.⁶¹ Another indication of insufficient enforcement is the lack of domestic prosecutions for serious violations committed during the Liberian civil wars.

Despite widespread reports of atrocities including massacres, and torture, perpetrators have still not been prosecuted within Liberia's domestic courts.

2.1.1.3 Weak Enforcement of Accountability Obligations under Human Rights Treaties

Liberia is a state party to several international human rights treaties that impose obligations on states to ensure accountability for serious violation of human rights. Notably, Liberia ratified the African Charter on Human and people's rights (ACHPR) in 1982; it furthermore committed to the ratification of the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Establishment of an African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights (the Protocol) in 1998, a treaty established to complement the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights by ensuring enforcement of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights.⁶²

Even though the African charter is a human rights treaty but it imposes an obligation to ensure accountability for serious human rights violations such as unlawful killings, torture, and inhumane treatment. Liberia is not subject to the jurisdiction of the African Court on Human and People's Rights, because the treaty that established the court has not been ratified by the State. However, the violation of such human right instrument would constitute international crimes when committed on widespread or systematic. Article 1 of the African Charter obliges state to adopt legislative and other measures necessary to give effect to the right guaranteed under the charter. In situation involving large scale violation such as mass killing, this obligation implies a duty on a state to prosecute and punish those responsible⁶³. However, the failure to adequately implement such obligations within the Liberia's domestic legal system has contributed to continued impunity for serious international crimes.

⁶¹ Fourth Geneva Convention, *supra* note 27, art. 146.

⁶² African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights, "*Liberia commits to ratification of the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Establishment of an African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights*" (African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights, 2024).

⁶³ African Charter on Human's and People's Rights of 1981, Art. 1.

Like the African Charter, Liberia ratified the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) in 2004. Consequently, the effective domestication of international crimes is essential not only for the compliance with international criminal law but also for fulfilling Liberia's broader human rights obligations under the ICCPR. For example, it was through the fulfillment of this convention and in line with its recommendation for gross human Rights violations, that the TRC included a list of individuals recommended to be barred from holding public offices for thirty years. Even though, this recommendation was not upheld. The Supreme Court of Liberia ruled in a case that the recommendation on prosecution of persons for gross human rights violations and war crimes, were unconstitutional. Therefore, this recommendation was not implemented.⁶⁴

Under article 2(3) of the ICCPR, states are required to ensure that individuals whose rights are violated have access to an effective remedy before competent judicial authorities.⁶⁵ Similarly, this imposed obligations on states to provide effective remedies and ensure accountability where serious violations occurred.⁶⁶ Yet, Liberia failure to incorporate international crimes into its domestic criminal law framework significantly undermines its ability to fulfill these obligations.

In this regard, the failure to effectively implement the accountability obligations specified in the ICCPR and the African Charter contributes to the challenge of domestication of international crimes in Liberia. This gap between treaty obligations and actual accountability reflects weaknesses in Liberia's enforcement of its international human rights commitments. And it provides requirements for effective remedies and accountability that underscore the importance of establishing a legal and institutional framework capable of prosecuting serious violations. Strengthening the implementation of these human rights obligations would therefore support broader efforts to combat impunity and promote accountability for international crimes within Liberia's domestic legal system.

⁶⁴ Centre for Civil and Political Rights, "*ICCPR Implementation in Liberia*"; Report of Civil Society Organizations in Reply to the List of Issue" 2018, p. 7.

⁶⁵ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966, Art. 2(3)

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*

2.2 Structural Deficiencies in Domestic Legal Framework

While the previous section examined Liberia's difficulties in fulfilling its international treaties obligations, the challenges surrounding the domestication of international crimes cannot fully be understood without considering the limitation within the country domestic and institutional frameworks. Accordingly, this section focuses on the structural deficiencies in Liberia domestic legal frameworks that continues to hinder the effective domestication of international crimes in Liberia.

Liberia's dualist system means that international treaties, while potentially influencing the interpretation of domestic laws, do not directly become part of the country's enforceable laws unless they are specifically translated into domestic legislation.⁶⁷ One of the primary challenges to the domestication of international crimes in Liberia lies within the domestic legal framework itself. Despite the mentioned ratification as a dualist State, the incorporation of international crimes into national law still remains incomplete and fragmented. Lack of legal provisions for international crimes, outdated criminal law framework, lack of specific or hybrid tribunal are all legal challenges hindering the domestication of international crimes.

2.2.1 Absence of Domestic Criminalization of International Crimes

The current criminal law frameworks of Liberia did not incorporate international crimes. There is no provision in the penal law, criminal procedure law or any statutory law that specified or criminalized international crimes, Genocide, war crimes, crime Against Humanity and Crime of Aggression.⁶⁸ Even though there is a legal duty to prosecute those responsible for serious violations of international human rights and humanitarian law, but there's still a gap in fully incorporating all international crimes as defined under international law.⁶⁹ This means that while Liberia has a responsibility to prosecute these crimes, its legal framework may not be fully equipped to do so according to international standards.

In a submission made to the United Nations Human Rights Committee, 76 African an inter-governmental organization made a call that the Liberian government should undertake fair

⁶⁷ J Medaglia, *“Direct Treaty Implementation in National Legal Systems*, Centre for International Sustainable Development Law, 2018, p.8.

⁶⁸ Liberian Code of Law Revised, Volume 1, Title 2 relating to Criminal Procedure, 1979

⁶⁹ X “The Advocate for Human Rights” available at <https://upr-info.org/sites/default/files/documents/2013-09/ahrtheadvocatesforhumanright> accessed March 8, 2026,

and credible prosecutions of international crimes committed during its two civil wars.⁷⁰ The organization made it known in its report the need for a legislative reform specifically on the penal law in order for it to meet modern international standards.

The current Liberia Criminal law framework primarily governs by its law on offences and punishment (penal code), criminal procedure law and other revised code of laws recognize and criminalizes a range of domestic offences like, Crimes Against Persons, Crimes Against Property, Crimes Against the State, public order offences, sexual and Gender-Based Violence (SGBV) Offences, Drug and Narcotics offences.⁷¹ While the criminal law addresses these ordinary crimes, it also lacks provisions to deal with crimes or grave breaches of international humanitarian law. This limits the country's ability to pursue justice for past war-era abuses or fulfill its obligations under international treaties like the Rome Statute. Hence, the lack of legal provisions on international crimes can be attributed to the level of inadequate criminal law framework and other constitutional constraints.

2.2.2 Inadequate Criminal law framework for Prosecuting International Crimes

Liberia's inadequate criminal law framework particularly the penal law and criminal procedure law remains in force but faces significant challenges due to its functional obsolescence and its failure to incorporate international criminal norms. The frameworks are further complicated by a dual justice system, where customary law practices coexist with the formal legal system, sometimes leading to conflicts and inconsistencies. Liberia's penal law framework faces challenges due to its age, as the current Penal Code is from 1976 and lacks some comprehensive updates. This outdated framework creates inconsistencies with modern legal standards.⁷²

The criminal procedure law of Liberia was enacted in 1969. The penal code of Liberia was also enacted in 1976, and went under amendment in 2005, where gang rape was criminalized.⁷³ In 2008, there was an act to amend chapter 14 and sub-chapter 15 of the penal law of 1976 by adding four sections thereby making crimes of armed robbery, terrorism, and hijacking respectively

⁷⁰ X “Liberia: 76 Groups Seek Justice for War Crimes”, available at <https://www.hrw.org/news/2018/07/05/liberia-76-groups-seek-justice-war-crimes> accessed February 23, 2026

⁷¹ Title 26, Liberian Penal Codes Revised of (1978, as amended)

⁷² Wayama foundation “Accountability in Liberia” available at <https://justiceafriqueouest.wayamo.com/en/country/liberia/>? accessed February 23, 2026

⁷³ Refworld “An act to amend the new penal code chapter 14 sections 14.70 And 14.71 and to provide for gang rape” available at <https://www.refworld.org/legal/legislation/natlegbod/2005/en/14724> accessed February 23, 2026

capital offenses, and providing punishment thereof. In 2019, a repealed was carried-out on section 11.11, 11.12, 11.14 of the penal law that decriminalized criminal libel against the president, sedition and criminal malevolence. Despite some of these amendments, there is still no comprehensive inclusion of international crimes, genocide, crimes against humanity, war crimes.

2.2.3 Constitutional Constraints on Domestication

Beyond the absence of specific legislation criminalizing international crimes and inadequate criminal law frameworks, there is a deeper constitutional constraint that also shapes Liberia's capacity to domesticate and prosecute such offences. The 1986 Constitution of Liberia establishes foundational principles that govern the creation and enforcement of criminal law, including constitutional supremacy, the principle of legality (*nullum crimen sine lege*), and the prohibition of *ex post facto* laws.⁷⁴

The principle of Legality, "*nullum crimen sine Lege*" and *ex post facto* are anchored in Article 21 of the 1986 Constitution of Liberia. it provides that "no person shall be made subject to any law or punishment which was not in effect at the time of commission of an offense, nor shall the Legislature enact any bill of attainder or *ex post facto* law".⁷⁵ It is re-echoed in Section 2.1 of Title 26 of the Liberian code of law revised (penal law) thereby giving statutory effects to this principle by defining what constitutes a crime. It holds that "a person commits an offense only if he voluntarily engages in conduct, including an act, an omission or possession in violation of a statute which provides that the conduct is an offense".⁷⁶ This section likewise confirms that since there is no domestic Statute for war crimes or crime against humanity, the conduct technically does not violate penal law even if it violates international treaties. This reflects not a rejection of international obligations, but a constitutional structure in which legislative enactment is a prerequisite for criminal liability. Article 34(j) of the 1986 constitution empowered the legislature to establish various categories of criminal offenses and provide for their punishment. Since section 2.1 of the penal law strictly requires a Statute to define an offence⁷⁷, the constitutional power given to the legislature as enshrined under Article 34(j)⁷⁸ has not been exercised to incorporate core

⁷⁴ Constitution of Liberia, 1986, Art.21.

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*

⁷⁶ Title 26 of the Liberian Code of law Revised(Penal Law of Liberia), Section 2.1

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*

⁷⁸ Constitution of Liberia, *supra* note 74, art.34(j)

international crimes into domestic law. This structural gap emerges between Liberia's international commitments and its domestic prosecutorial capacity. In practical terms, the principle of legality operates as a constraint on prosecution unless and until Parliament enacts legislation defining those international crimes within the national legal framework.

Furthermore, the prohibition of the *ex post facto* principle under article 21 of the 1986 Constitution also presents a constitutional constraint on domesticating international crimes. The provision through this principle prohibits the retroactive creation of criminal liability. That no person can be punished for an act which was not criminal at the time it was committed and the parliament cannot enact a retroactive law. This means any subsequent legislative efforts to incorporate the core international crimes; there would be a constitutional question of whether such enactment may be applied to conduct predating their adoption.

In light of this constitutional supremacy, any domestication statute must conform with article 21, which might limit Liberia's ability to reactively prosecute international crimes. Notwithstanding it has obligation under the Rome Statute. Even though there has been scholarly debate on the legal challenge arising from such issues. Some argue that by prosecuting international crimes is not reactive if those crimes already existed in customary international law.⁷⁹ This was the case of Rwanda. The country faced a significant constitutional challenge arising from the prohibition of *ex post facto* criminal legislation⁸⁰. However, Rwanda adopted a pragmatic approach by relying on the doctrine of dual incrimination, where, the crime of genocide was a crime under the Genocide Convention to which Rwanda was a party and customary international law. Yet, its constitutional structure reflects a predominantly monist orientation in which ratified treaties may have direct domestic effect.⁸¹

While these principles are essential for protecting individual rights and ensuring legal certainty, they may also create a significant challenge in domesticating and prosecuting international crimes. The absence of specific domestic legislation criminalizing international crimes therefore interacts with the principle of legality and *ex post facto* to create a significant barrier to accountability.

⁷⁹ Payam Akhavan, "The Perils of Progressive Jurisprudence: The Nullum Crimen Sine Lege Principle in International Criminal Law" current legal problem journal, 2022 p.56.

⁸⁰ *Ibid.*

⁸¹ J.B. MUTANGANA, "Domestic prosecution of international Crimes, perspectives on cases refereed to Rwanda" 2014, p.3.

Without legislative reform that clearly incorporates international crimes into Liberia's criminal law framework, domestic courts may face serious constitutional limitations when attempting to prosecute past atrocities. Addressing this challenge requires deliberate legislative action by the Liberian Parliament to establish a clear legal basis for the prosecution of international crimes in accordance with both constitutional safeguards and international legal obligations.

Despite these Constitutional constraints, there were also recommendation made by the Liberia TRC for the establishment of an extraordinary tribunal at the end of the Liberian civil war. This ad hoc court would exercise its jurisdiction over crimes committed during the Liberian civil war. The current lack of this court also possesses a significant challenge.⁸²

2.2.4 Absence of Specialize or Hybrid Court for the Prosecution of International Crimes

Another challenge affecting the domestication of international crimes is the absence of specialize or hybrid court. one of the major recommendations made by the Liberian TRC was for the establishment of an Extraordinary Criminal Court (ECC) for Liberia, which would try suspected perpetrators for egregious domestic crimes, gross violations of human rights and serious humanitarian law violations, committed in Liberia between January 1979 and 14 October 2003. The Commission also made recommendations on the form of the court, which should be hybrid in nature, with both domestic and international elements. Further recommendations were made on the nomination of national and international judges, prosecutors, and other staffs.⁸³

The Truth and Reconciliation Commission Consolidated final report states that the "TRC hereby recommends the establishment of an Extraordinary Criminal Court for Liberia" to try all persons recommended by the TRC for the commission of gross human rights violations including the violation of international humanitarian law, international human right law, war crimes, and economic crimes including but not limited to, killing, gang rape, multiple rape, forced recruitment, sexual slavery, forced labor, exposure to deprivation, missing.⁸⁴ The absence of such a specialized or hybrid judicial mechanism creates a legal gap in the prosecution of international crimes. Without

⁸² TRC, "*final consolidated Report*", volume II, 2009, p.268.

⁸³Wayamafoundation"AccountabilityinLiberia"availableat <https://justiceafriqueouest.wayamo.com/en/country/liberia/>? accesse February 24, 2026

⁸⁴ TRC *Supra* note 82, p. 268.

a court specifically mandated to adjudicate these offences, the incorporation of international crimes into the domestic legal framework becomes largely symbolic.

International law mandates trials for institutional enforcement of international crime and as a state to many international treaties, it is binding to uphold certain minimum standards and ensure that serious violations of human rights and war crimes are appropriately investigated and prosecuted.⁸⁵

Beyond the absence of specialize or hybrid court, Liberia also faces significant legal barriers that undermine the prosecution of international crimes. One of the most contentious among these is the continued reliance on amnesty provisions adopted in the aftermath of the civil conflict.

2.2.5 Amnesty provision as an Obstacle to the Domestication of International Crimes in Liberia

Another significant legal challenge to the domestication of international crimes in Liberia is the existence of broad amnesty. In 2003, the Transitional Liberian Government passed legislation that granted immunity for both civil and criminal proceedings against all persons within the jurisdiction of Liberia for acts or crimes committed between 1989 and 2003.⁸⁶ Frontpage Africa a prominent newspaper in Liberia made a publication on May 25 2021, that it has obtained an Act, titled ““An Act to Grant Immunity from Both Civil and Criminal Proceeding against All Persons within the Jurisdiction of the Republic of Liberia from Acts or Crimes Committed During the Civil War from December 1989 to August 2003.” Published in August 2003.⁸⁷

The Act was not repealed before the establishment of the TRC, which in its 2009 report was resolute in its recommendation that in accordance with international standards, no amnesty should be granted for the heinous crimes that were committed in Liberia. In the view of the Liberian TRC, granting amnesty would not only be unacceptable and immoral but would also promote impunity.⁸⁸

Furthermore, a Comprehensive peace Agreement (CPA) a peace agreement signed in Accra in 2003 included provisions for a broad amnesty, which, while intended to promote peace, legally

⁸⁵ Human Rights Watch “Q & A Justice for Civil Wars – Era Crimes in Liberia” available at <https://www.hrw.org/news/2019/04/01/qa-justice-civil-wars-era-crimes-liberia#> accessed February 25, 2026.

⁸⁶ P. Hayner “*Negotiating peace in Liberia*, Preserving the possibility for Justice” 2007, p. 15.

⁸⁷ L. Dodoo, *FrontPageAfrica Obtains a 2003 Act of Legislature Granting General Amnesty to All Partakers of the 14-Year Civil Conflict*, Front Page Africa, 2021.

⁸⁸ Wayama foundation “Accountability in Liberia” available at <https://justiceafriqueouest.wayamo.com/en/country/liberia/?> accessed February 26, 2026

undermines the incorporation and enforcement of international criminal norms in Liberia's domestic legal system.⁸⁹ Consequently, amnesty remains a key legal barrier to the effective domestication and prosecution of international crimes.

2.3 Institutional Challenges hindering the Domestication of International crimes

Domesticating international crimes in Liberia requires more than a legal reform. Even if these crimes were to be domesticated, institutional weakness would still severely limit the country capacity to implement and enforce international law.

2.3.1 Limited Judicial Capacity in prosecuting International Crimes

Liberia's judiciary is widely considered limited, facing several challenges like inadequate funding, and a lack of qualified personnel, which significantly hinder its effectiveness. The Liberian justice system is historically limited and will need the infusion of international participation alongside Liberian judges to try atrocity crimes. The proposed framework is valuable to ensure the bench's actual and perceived independence, impartiality, and expertise. This weakness contributes to a lack of public trust, leading some to resort to mob justice, and creates an environment where impunity can flourish.⁹⁰

Many factors including impunity, lack of accountability, lack of training and capacity, create both incentives and serve as barrier within the Justice System. Moreover, the formal legal system is largely inaccessible, financially unaffordable and overly time-consuming for the average person and customary channels of justice are largely geared towards promoting reconciliation rather than accountability.⁹¹ Addressing the issues of limited legal and institutional frameworks in Liberia is much needed. During the 1989-2003 civil wars, the judiciary institutions were systematically weakened. Courts are chronically and severely understaffed, which results in large gaps of delays and inconsistent enforcement of even the most basic laws.⁹²

⁸⁹LiberiaComprehensivePeaceAgreement,availableat https://www.usip.org/sites/default/files/file/resources/collections/peace_agreements/liberia_08182003. Accessed February 24, 2026

⁹⁰ Liberia's Compliance with the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights Report available at <https://www.amnesty.org/fr/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/AFR3487352018ENGLISH.pdf> accessed February 24, 2026

⁹¹ N. Myers, Liberia, *The high level of corruption in both the Executive and Judiciary branches of government t serves as an impediment to socioeconomic development*. Policy paper, The Willy Brandt School of public policy, 2017, p. 5.

⁹² R. Zayzay, "Liberia and the Implementation of International Law - Challenges and Prospects", the Liberian investigator, Monrovia, 2025.

Several reports have emerged that it has human resource, financial and infrastructural constraints resulting in a backlog of cases that undermines access to justice. Eighty percent (80%) of Liberians rely on traditional leaders, guided by customary practices that are inherently gender discriminatory, to resolve disputes. A public perception survey of security and justice institutions showed that the public has higher trust and confidence in the informal justice system (69%) as compared to the formal justice system (31%).⁹³

Similarly, a study on the perception of the courts across all 16 counties in Liberia revealed that only 28 percent of Liberians felt judges treated them equally; 23 percent felt that judgments were the same for everyone; and 31 percent trusted their judges, suggesting a major lack of trust in the court system, with little variation across counties.⁹⁴

The Bertelsmann Stiftung's Transformation Index (BTI) a biennial assessment that analyzes and developing and transition countries on their progress toward democracy and rule of law, held in its 2024 report on Liberia that the statutory judiciary is formally independent and institutionally differentiated but characterized by severe functional deficits. Judges have reportedly faced undue influence from the private sector and government officials. Corruption of judges and juries (used in circuit court trials) constitutes a major obstacle to fair and transparent trials. Judicial sitting days are limited, and the absence of judiciary personnel often leads to trial delays. The report further stressed that the cost of accessing the judicial system is high, particularly for the rural population. Expenses incurred by police and others, such as transportation of accused offenders, often fall on plaintiffs, and that there has been an increasing effort to strengthen executive control over the judiciary.⁹⁵

Moreover, adjudicating international crimes requires judges who possess specialized training and familiarity with international humanitarian and criminal law principles. In the absence of sufficient judicial expertise and institutional support, domestic courts may face serious difficulties in interpreting and applying these legal standards, thereby undermining the effective domestication

⁹³ UNDP Liberia "Strengthening the Rule of Law in Liberia" available at <https://www.undp.org/liberia/projects/strengthening-rule-law-liberia-justice-and-security-liberian-people-phase> accessed February 26, 2026

⁹⁴ World Bank "2023 Jupiter Assessment improving Justice in Liberia" Washington DC, 2023, p.44

⁹⁵ BTI "Liberia Country Report 2024" available at <https://bti-project.org/en/reports/country-report/LBR#pos5> accessed February 27, 2026

and prosecution of international crimes. It is however, a reality that persistent limitation in the judiciary tends to undermined access to justice and due process.

2.3.2 Financial Constraints Affecting the Criminal Justice System

Despite judicial limitation, there are other factors like financial constraints and poor investigative and prosecutorial capacity that also serve as an institutional barrier for prosecuting complex international crimes. Prosecuting international crimes often requires significant financial resources for investigations, witness protection, expert analysis, and court proceedings. Many countries lack the necessary budget to adequately address these challenges.

The judiciary often receives less than 2% of the total government expenditure, with significant portions allocated to fixed costs like salaries, leaving little for operational needs and infrastructure development. Adequate budgeting of the judiciary is critical for the effective delivery of justice.⁹⁶

2.3.3 Weak Investigative and Prosecutorial Mechanism to Handle International Crimes

Liberia currently lacks a specialized investigators or prosecutors trained to handle complex crimes like genocide or crimes against humanity. The Liberia National police whose function is to protect fundamental rights and freedom⁹⁷ has no war crimes unit. There's also no infrastructure for forensic evidence collection, chain of custody, or analysis. For example, the Liberia National Police LNP, the main organ responsible to investigate crimes faces severe resource constraints, hindering its ability to conduct thorough investigations.⁹⁸ In a 2012 report, the UN reached what it called a “sobering” assessment of the LNP’s policing capacity, and expressed concern about the extensive logistics deficiencies. The report also noted that while the development of security institutions had received considerable attention, there had been less of a focus on governance and accountability mechanisms for these institutions, which remain weak.⁹⁹ These legal and institutional challenges have so far hinder the domestication of international crimes under the Liberian criminal law. Addressing these challenges would require not just legislative reforms but also deep investment in judicial capacity building and institutional integrity.

⁹⁶ Bosio, Erica, “*Reforming Justice, Engaging with Countries on Judicial Budgets*” Prosperity Notes Series, 2024

⁹⁷ Liberia National Police act of 2015, Section 22.72.

⁹⁸ X “Africa Organized Crime index”, available at <https://africa.ocindex.net/2021/country/liberia> accessed February 24, 2026

⁹⁹ X “No Money, No Justice” available <https://www.hrw.org/report/2013/08/22/no-money-no-justice/police-corruption-and-abuse-liberi> accessed February 24, 2026

CHAPTER THREE: PROPOSED MECHANISMS FOR OVERCOMING LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL CHALLENGES HINDERING THE DOMESTICATION OF INTERNATIONAL CRIMES IN LIBERIA

This chapter examines the necessary measures for overcoming the challenges enlisted in chapter two in domesticating international crimes under the Liberia criminal law framework. In doing so, it examines potential reforms aimed at improving Liberia's capacity to address international crimes. Building on these, the chapter also draws a comparative insight from post-conflict jurisdiction such as Rwanda and Sierra Leone, which have adopted different approaches to addressing serious international crimes through domestic reforms and specialize judicial mechanism.

3.1 Reforming Liberia's Legal and Institutional Framework for the Prosecution of International Crimes

This section particularly examines the necessary reforms aimed at overcoming the challenges hindering the effective domestication of international crimes under the Liberian.

3.1.1 Enactment of an International Crimes Act in Liberia

One major solution for integrating international crimes within Liberia national criminal law framework, is by drafting and enacting a separate act basically on international crimes. ¹⁰⁰Such legislation would domesticate international crimes in line with Liberia international legal obligations and primary responsibility with the Rome Statute.

Enacting an international crimes act has emerged as the principal means for integrating international criminal law into domestic jurisdiction.¹⁰¹ A State exercises jurisdiction within its own territory. Such jurisdiction includes the power to make law, to interpret or apply the law, and to take action to enforce the law.¹⁰²

¹⁰⁰ M. Booth-Matthisjssen, "Key Provision of the Dutch International Crimes Act 2003" Netherland year book of international journal, 2024, p.256

¹⁰¹ *Id.*, p.296

¹⁰² ICRC, "General Principles of International Criminal Law" Advisory service on IHL, p.2, 2021

This position has been clearly illustrated by many State around the world. For example, in 2002, the country enacted what it terms as “Act 27” relating to the implementation of the Rome statute.¹⁰³ Part one to three of the act reconized the core international crimes, genocide, war crimes and crimes against humanity by copying the definitons of these crimes from the Rome Statute.¹⁰⁴

By adopting such Act, Liberia would also ensure that the definition of genocide, war crimes, crime Against humanity and crime of Aggression are fully incorporated with internationally recognize Standards. This would also facilitate important principles of international criminal law that are often absent from ordinary domestic legislation. These include modes of liability such as command responsibility and individual criminal responsibility. When drafted, the International Criminal Acts would likewise provide penalties of international crimes, established the jurisdiction of Domestic Courts over these crimes, remove immunities as it hinders the effectiveness of laws, and ensure victim participation and a comprehensive witness protection mechanism.

3.1.2 Reform of Liberia’s Penal Law to Incorporate International Crimes

Another key mechanism for domesticating international crimes in Liberia is by reforming the national penal framework to expressly incorporate international crimes. At present, the current penal law lacks an inclusion of international crimes, and only addresses conventional domestic offences.¹⁰⁵ Through this reform, a new chapter or provisions would be use to integrate international crimes with offenses based on the definitions provided by the Rome Statue and the Geneva Conventions.

The penal code reform for accountability would also focus on strengthening the legal frameworks to address impunity, particularly for gross international human rights violations. Key areas include repealing outdated provisions, enhancing prosecutorial capacity, and establishing mechanisms for victim participation in legal processes. In addition to defining these offences, the reformed legislation could incorporate key principles governing individual criminal responsibility, and command responsibility, and other forms of participation in international crimes.

These provisions are particularly important given that international crimes are often committed within complex chains of command and involve multiple actors at different levels of responsibility.

¹⁰³ South Africa, Implementation of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, Act 27 of 2002.

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁵ Penal law, *supra* note 76, Sec 1.1-51.3

Reforming the penal law to include international crimes is an integral to the enjoyment of basic human rights, which is also an essential precondition to social inclusion.

The periodic review of the national human right plan of Liberia from 2013-2018 recommended that several measures be carryout in the area of the administration of justice to accelerate the reform of the judicial system, to fight against abuses of preventive detention, and to draft and transmit the report expected since 2005 by the Committee against Torture. Also Intensify efforts to strengthen the criminal justice system, especially in view of promoting accountability.¹⁰⁶

Finally, Procedural provisions should also be included in the criminal procedure law of Liberia, allowing universal jurisdiction over international crimes and international corporation like mutual assistance and extradition. Ultimately by reforming Liberia penal law to incorporate international crimes would represent a crucial step towards overcoming the legal barriers identified in the previous chapter in domesticating international crimes in Liberia.

3.1.3 Establishment of a Specialize or Hybrid Court for the Prosecution of International Crimes

Another important step for ensuring accountability for international crimes in Liberia would be the establishment of a hybrid or specialized criminal court.

In their consolidated report, the Liberia Commissioners of the TRC determine that a criminal court with the competence and jurisdiction to adjudicate criminal responsibility for individuals, armed groups and other entities that the TRC determines were responsible for ‘egregious’ domestic crimes, ‘gross’ violations of human rights and ‘serious’ humanitarian law violations is appropriate. Such institution shall be specifically endowed with the authority and jurisdiction to adjudicate domestic, IHRL and IHL violations.¹⁰⁷ It determined that certain group of people were responsible for the commission of human rights violations.

In its report of 2009, the TRC specified that these group of people as recommended by the entity violated international law, by committing acts like, killing, gang rape, multiple rape, forced recruitment, sexual slavery.¹⁰⁸ In light of this, the creation of a hybrid court was recommended.

¹⁰⁶ GOL “National Human Rights Plans of Liberia” available at https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/Issues/NHRA/Liberia_en.pdf accessed February 28, 2026

¹⁰⁷ Truth and Reconciliation commission findings *supra* note 7, p. 6

¹⁰⁸ TRC *supra* note 82, P. 268.

The Creation of a specialized or hybrid court could significantly enhance the country's ability to prosecute crimes such as war crimes, and crimes against humanity committed during the nation civil conflicts.

Hybrid court have proven effective in addressing similar post-conflict contexts. A notable example is the Special court for Sierra Leone, which was established through an agreement between the Government of Sierra Leone and the United Nation.¹⁰⁹

The court combined both international and domestic judges and applied both international and national law, thereby strengthening domestic judicial capacity while ensuring adherence to international legal standards.

Adopting a similar hybrid model in Liberia could address many of the institutional challenges identified in the previous chapter. It would also allow Liberia to benefit from international expertise while simultaneously strengthening the domestic justice system. It could also help ensure that prosecutions are conducted in accordance with international legal standards, including those reflected in the Rome Statute.

By creating a specialized judicial forum, capable of addressing complex international crimes, Liberia would take a significant step toward fulfilling its international obligation and strengthening the domestication of international criminal law into its national criminal law framework.

3.1.4 Reconciling the Principle of Legality with the Prosecution of International Crimes

Another major legal mechanism for strengthening the domestication of international crimes in Liberia involves addressing the constitutional constraints prohibiting the *ex post facto* laws and the doctrine of *nullum crimen sine lege* specified under article 21 of the 1986 constitution¹¹⁰ and section 2.1 of Title 26 of the 1976 code of Law Revised.¹¹¹

While these criminal law principles are essential for safeguarding individual rights and ensuring legal certainty, they may also create challenges when states attempt to prosecute international crimes that were not explicit incorporated into domestic laws at the time of their commission.

¹⁰⁹ C. Jalloh, "*Special Court of Sierra Leone, Achieving Justice*" Michigan Journal of International Law, 2011, p.3

¹¹⁰ Constitution of Liberia, *supra* note 74, art.21.

¹¹¹ Penal law, *supra* note 76, sec.2.1

If Liberia is to domesticate international crimes and attempt to prosecute these international offences in national courts for past violations of international humanitarian and human rights laws, such move may raise constitutional concern regarding retroactive criminal liability. Addressing this tension require a careful legal reform aimed at reconciling the principle of legality with Liberia's international legal obligations to prosecute serious crimes.

One possible approach is to recognize that international crimes were already prohibited under customary international law at the time they were committed. This interpretation had been adopted in several international tribunals.

On the defence motion for interlocutory appeal on jurisdiction in the jurisprudence of the *Prosecutor v Tadic*, the appeal chamber held in paragraph 76 of its ruling that there is no question but that crimes against humanity form part of customary international law.¹¹²

The chamber specified that they are recognized under Article 6(c) of the Nuremberg Charter of 8 August 1945, Article II(1)(c) of Law No. 10 of the Control Council for Germany of 20 December 1945 and Article 5(c) of the Tokyo Charter of 26 April 1946, three major documents promulgated in the aftermath of World War II.¹¹³

International law do recognize that the prosecution of international crimes does not explicit violate the principle of legality because the acts were already criminal under international law even if they were not codified under domestic legislation.¹¹⁴

Another potential mechanism involves legislative clarification. This could be done through the enactment of comprehensive legislation that incorporates international crimes into domestica legal system while acknowledging their status under international law. Such reforms could help ensure that domestic prosecutions are conducted in a manner consistent with both constitutional protections and Liberia's obligation under international criminal law.

¹¹² *Prosecutor V. Tadic*, Case No.: IT-94-1-A, ICTY Appeal Chamber 2, judgement, August 1995

¹¹³ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁴ A. Bufalini, "*The Principle of Legality and the Role of Customary International Law in the Interpretation of the ICC Statute*", *The Law and Practice of international courts and Tribunals*, 2015, p.5

By carefully addressing these constitutional constraints, Liberia can strengthen the legal foundation for prosecuting serious international crimes while maintaining respect for fundamental principles of criminal justice.

3.1.5 Strengthening Liberia's Judicial and Prosecutorial Capacity for International Crimes

Strengthening the judicial and prosecutorial capacity is another significant prerequisite for the effective domestication of international crimes in Liberia.

These offences often involve complex legal doctrines, evidentiary standards, and procedural mechanisms that often exceeds the experience of domestic justice systems. Consequently, building the competence of Judges, prosecutors, investigators as recommended by the Liberia TRC is essential for Liberia to exercise its primary responsibility under the Rome Statute of the international Criminal Court.¹¹⁵

Since domestic prosecution of international crimes also requires specialized knowledge of international criminal law, international humanitarian law, and human rights law. Moreover, capacity building initiatives are necessary to enable that the Liberia judiciary and prosecutorial services are fully equipped to investigate, prosecute and adjudicate international crimes according to international legal standards.

By doing this, there will also be a need for a specialize international crimes unit within the national prosecutorial and investigative body. Specialize units are no panacea for ending impunity and work best as part of an integrated approach to tackling broader impunity. Eventhough the need for a perfect model of a specialize unit much depends on each country legal and institutional framework.

However, past and current practice demonstrates that despite the complexities involved, holding perpetrators of serious international crimes accountable is possible where there is a commitment to make the necessary practice arrangements.¹¹⁶

A specialized international crimes units will be charge to exclusively investigate and prosecute international crimes and their staffs will be train in complex case management.¹¹⁷ The importance

¹¹⁵ TRC, *supra* note 82, p.269.

¹¹⁶J. Schurr, "*The practice of specialized war crimes unit*", International federation of human rights, 2010, p. 28.

¹¹⁷ *Id.*,29

of said units would lie in their abilities to develop expertise in handling the unique features of international crimes.¹¹⁸

Comparative practice also demonstrates the effectiveness of such mechanisms. In many jurisdictions where international crimes have been domesticated, jurisdictions, there is an established specialized war crimes unit to investigate international crimes under the principle of universal jurisdiction. These units have significantly improved the ability of national authorities to prosecute complex international cases.¹¹⁹

Even where legal frameworks exist, the inability to investigate crimes properly renders prosecution ineffective. Domestication is not only a matter of incorporating international crimes into domestic law, but also ensuring that the state has the practical capacity to investigate and prosecute such crimes. For Liberia, the establishment of a similar specialized unit would also represent a crucial step toward strengthening domestic capacity for the prosecution of international crimes.

3.1.5.1 Enhancing Witness Protection and Victims Participation

Another essential component in strengthening judicial capacity building is the development of an effective mechanism for witness protection and victim participation. Witness protection is an essential condition given the scale and nature of international crimes.

It is therefore equally important to establish an effective witness and victim participation mechanism, as seen in several post-conflict nations that have incorporated international crimes in their domestic laws. Especially protective mechanisms recognized by the ICC such as anonymity orders, relocation programs, and psychological support services for witnesses. These mechanisms are essential in ensuring that witnesses can safely contribute to the judicial process.¹²⁰

In addition to this witness protection, victims' participation has become a modern feature of modern international criminal justice.

Unlike traditional criminal proceedings, which often treat victims solely as witnesses, international criminal law increasingly recognizes victims as active participants in the justice process. Whether victim as participant or victim as witness, strengthening judicial and prosecutorial capacity

¹¹⁸ Australian Center for International Justice, "*Challenging Impunity, why Australia needs a permanent, specialized international crimes unit*" Policy paper, 2023, p.22.

¹¹⁹ J. Schuur, *supra* note 116, p. 23.

¹²⁰ Rome Statute, *supra* note 11, art. 64.

alongside the development of effective witness would significantly enhance Liberia's ability to domesticate international crimes within its criminal justice system.

3.1.6 Strengthening International Corporation and Legal assistance for the effective Domestication of International crimes

While domestication is often understood as the incorporation of international crimes into national criminal law framework, its practical realization depends on the ability of a state to investigate and prosecute such crimes effectively.

Given the trans-national nature of international crimes, strengthening international corporation and legal assistance would constitutes an essential mechanism for the effective domestication of international crimes. It is through international corporations that domestication is transformed from a legal concept into a functional system of accountability.¹²¹

The results of regulatory processes developed within state and supranational levels differ in scope and regulatory technique, lacking coherence and specificity. These shortcomings therefore indicate the need for integration of judicial cooperation through mutual assistance aimed at a global codification that will enable States to be cumulative and alternative in order to ensure their effectiveness.¹²²

The importance of mutual legal assistance in the prosecution of crimes with transnational elements has been noted by the supreme court of Canada in the jurisprudence of the *United States of America v. Cotroni* in 1989. The court stated that the investigation, prosecution and suppression of crime for the protection of the citizen and the maintenance of peace and public order is an important goal of all organized societies. The court further observed that the pursuit of these goals cannot realistically be confined within national boundaries.¹²³

This reasoning is particularly relevant in the context of international crimes, which by their nature often involve cross border elements, including the movement of perpetrators. The importance of

¹²¹ D. Liakopoulos, "International cooperation, legal assistance and the case of lacking states collaboration within the international criminal court" DERECHO, 2019, p.2.

¹²² *Ibid.*

¹²³ *United States of America v. Cotroni*; *United States of America v. El Zein*, Case. No 20035, 20036, Supreme court of Canada, judgement, June 1989.

international corporation in the prosecution of international crimes is further illustrated in the *Prosecutor v. Charles Taylor* before the Special court of Sierra Leone.

In that case the successful prosecution of the former head of state depending on the extensive corporation between many states. This includes the arrest and transfer of the accused from Nigeria and relocations of proceeding to the Hague¹²⁴. This demonstrates that without effective mechanism for corporation and mutual legal assistance, domestic and hybrid tribunals would face significant challenges. In essence, in the absence of effective mutual legal assistance and international cooperation, domestic legal systems may be unable to secure the presence of suspects for trial. International cooperation mechanisms, including extradition, mutual legal assistance, and joint investigative frameworks, would then play a crucial role in enabling domestic authorities to overcome such challenge.¹²⁵

Therefore, strengthening Liberia legal frameworks for international corporation would significantly enhance the country capacity to prosecute international crimes domestically. This is particularly important given the legacy of the country past civil conflict, where perpetrators may have been dispersed across multiple jurisdictions.

3.2 A Comparative insight from Sierra Leone and Rwanda on the Domestication of International crimes

By examining Rwanda's post-genocide legal reforms and Sierra Leone institutional mechanisms developed alongside the Special Court of Sierra Leone, this session seeks to analyze practical lessons and structural contrasts that may help in Liberia's ongoing efforts toward accountability.

3.2.1 Rwanda's Integration of International Crimes

The crime of genocide, crimes against humanity and war crimes are unanimously condemned by the international community. Within this ambit, a number of international treaties were adopted to these effects. However, most of them such as the 1948 Genocide Convention are not self-executing and require State parties to enact enabling legislations.¹²⁶ Rwanda being a party to the 1948

¹²⁴ Prosecutor V. Charles Taylor, Case No. SCSL-03-1-T, Judgement, Trial Chamber II, April 2011

¹²⁵ Manual on mutual Legal Assiatnce available at https://www.unodc.org/documents/organized-crime/Publications/Mutual_Legal_Assistance_Ebook accessed 3 March 23, 2026

¹²⁶ N. Dieudonne, "*The Application of International Criminal Law Under Rwandan Law*": Challenges and Lessons Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2764340>

Genocide Convention did not put in place an enabling legislation for that effect, which became a great challenge in prosecuting international crimes in the aftermath of the darkest part of Rwandan history (1994 Genocide against Tutsis). After all, it drew a lesson therefrom and currently all international core crimes are legislated.¹²⁷

Rwanda's interest with regard to the domestic application of international criminal law arose in the aftermath of the 1994 genocide against Tutsis and the initial prosecution and repression of international crimes. Even though it was confronted with two main challenges and those were the Rwandan legal landscape that was not set to accommodate the prosecution and repression of such atrocities and the judicial system's capacity that was scant to effectively and timely prosecute and punish the alleged perpetrators.¹²⁸

First, after the 1994 genocide, the Rwandan legal landscape was not ready to accommodate the prosecution and repression of international crimes, since none of the three international core crimes i.e. genocide, crime against humanity and war crimes were provided for and punished as such in Rwandan criminal law regime. State inspired violence directed against innocent civilians culminating into the culture of impunity prevailed for so long and no attempts were ever made to bring the perpetrators of crimes emanating from this violence to justice, and as a result, Rwandan society succumbed to the culture of impunity.¹²⁹

However, the prosecution of the constitutive acts of genocide like murder and bodily harm as ordinary crime would deprive them their exceptional nature. In this regard, Rwanda could not let the constitutive acts of the crime of genocide and other international core crimes be prosecuted as ordinary crimes, but instead a pragmatic response was to be hunted for.

Moreover, the application of international criminal law in Rwanda could not be smooth as the then judicial system could not effectively and timely deal with the prosecution and repression of international crimes.

¹²⁷ N. Dieudonne, "*The Application of International Criminal Law Under Rwandan Law*": Challenges and Lessons Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2764340>

¹²⁸ J.B. MUTANGANA, "*Domestic prosecution of international Crimes, perspectives on cases referred to Rwanda*" 2014, p.3

¹²⁹ *Id.*, p.4.

There were legal challenges to prosecuting genocide crimes nationally. Although Rwanda is a signatory to the 1948 Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of Genocide and to the 1949 Geneva Conventions and their Protocols, by 1994 they had not been domesticated into national legislation, rendering prosecution of genocide crimes difficult.¹³⁰ In this regard, it is asserted that the majority of the judicial personnel vested with prosecuting and judging international crimes were non-professional lawyers who had undergone accelerated training sessions on substantive and procedural laws in order to deal with the unprecedented situation the country was faced with.¹³¹

Finally, despite the confronted challenges, Rwanda realize that it was high time to act with regard to putting in place the legal landscape and the judicial system that is responsive to international core crimes. To this end, the crime of genocide, crimes against and war crimes are currently legislated for. Moreover, the judicial system has been reformed with aim to build a competent judiciary where a strong court system has been developed to acclimatize the prosecution and repression of international crimes both under the auspices of universal and territorial jurisdictions.

3.2.1.1 Rwanda Penal Law Reform in Addressing International Crimes

With advice and support from the ICTR, Rwanda was able to succeed in its efforts at legislative reform. The pursuit of these reforms was motivated at least in part by its continued commitment to securing the referral of indictments from the ICTR. The country undertook an extensive overhaul of its Penal Code and Code of Criminal Procedure to modernize provisions and substantially reduce the range of criminal sentences, including for persons convicted of genocide ideology.¹³²

Today, Rwanda has modernized its criminal procedure and penal law on offences and penalties in general, ensuring alignment with international criminal justice standards. It included provisions on the prohibition of international crimes and provision on Individual criminal responsibility, Command responsibility irrelevance of official capacity and non-applicability of statutory limitations for core international crimes.

¹³⁰ P. Rowanda *el at.*, “*Changing Patterns of Acceptance. International Criminal Justice after the Rwandan Genocide*”, International Nuremberg principle academy, 2017, p.4

¹³¹ *Ibid.*

¹³² ICTR,” *Complementarity in Action, lesson Learned from the ICTR prosecutor referral of international criminal cases to national Jurisdiction*” 2015, p.26

According to Article 14 of the Rwanda law on offences and penalty, an international crime is a crime classified as such under international law the crime of genocide; the crime against humanity; war crimes.¹³³ The Law on offences and penalty likewise recognized, defined and punished these core international crimes. As a post-conflict nation, integrating these crimes was a major step taken to uphold its international legal commitments.

Despite the ratification and Integration of core international crimes, Rwanda National Courts have jurisdiction to try and prosecute these international crimes. The High Court hears both transnational and international crimes depending on their classification. They use the penal law and relevant Organic Laws as legal basis.

Article 42 of the law determining the jurisdiction of courts in Rwanda empowered the Specialized chamber of the High Court hearing International and transnational crimes¹³⁴ the jurisdiction to try at first instance all persons accused of committing international crimes, regardless of whether the person is a foreigner or national, or whether the crime was committed on the territory of Rwanda or outside its territory.

The law likewise empowered both the Intermediate Court and the Primary Court the jurisdiction over the crimes of genocide perpetrated against the Tutsi and crimes against humanity committed in Rwanda between 1st October 1990 and 31st December 1994.¹³⁵ Thereby holding individuals accountable for committing the crime of genocide and crime against humanity and also upholding the peremptory norm of *jus cogen* that Crime like genocide comes with a mandatory rule from which no derogation is permitted.

Another major contribution to judicial capacity building was the establishment of the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR). Established through a U.N Security Council Resolution 955, based on the request that was made by the Government of Rwanda to establish an international tribunal, for the sole purpose of prosecuting persons responsible for genocide and other serious violation of international law committed in the territory of Rwanda.

¹³³ Law n°68/2018 of 30/08/2018 Determining offences and Penalties in General, OG n° special of 27/09/2018, Art.14.

¹³⁴ Law N°30/2018 OF 02/06/2018 Determining the Jurisdiction of Courts in Rwanda, OG n° Special of 02/06/2018, Art. 42.

¹³⁵ *Id.*, art.26.

The Tribunal jurisdiction, both *ratione materiae* (subject matter) and *ratione personae* (personal), was defined by its Statute, which also outlined the crimes it could prosecute and the individuals it could hold accountable.

The ICTR is the first ever international tribunal to deliver verdicts in relation to genocide, and the first to interpret the definition of genocide set forth in the 1948 Geneva Convention. It is also the first international tribunal to define rape in international criminal law and to recognize rape as a means of perpetrating genocide. With its sister international tribunals and courts, the ICTR played a pioneering role in the establishment of a credible international criminal justice system, producing a substantial body of jurisprudence on genocide, crimes against humanity, war crimes, as well as forms of individual and superior responsibility. Since it opened in 1995, the Tribunal indicted 93 individuals whom it considered responsible for serious violations of international humanitarian law committed in Rwanda in 1994. Those indicted included high-ranking military and government officials, politicians, businessmen, as well as religious, militia, and media leaders.¹³⁶

In infrastructure improvement, a new witness protection unit (WPU) was created within the judiciary primarily to service those defence witnesses who might be disinclined to seek services from the Witness-Victims Services Unit (WVSU) located within the Prosecutor General's Office. Secondly, there was an established state-of-the-art detention facility, which even saw convicts from the special court of Sierra Leone. Finally, the nation expanded its legal assistance programs by allowing more flexibility in the application of procedures for reciprocal admission.¹³⁷

The applicability of international criminal within municipal law constitutes an area of discussion, and Rwanda is one of the countries, if not the first one that have been challenged in dealing with international criminal law, since apart from having ratified a multitude of conventions to that effect among others the genocide convention, no further step was taken to ensure that they can be applied domestically with ease.¹³⁸

However, from this perplexing application of international criminal law significant lessons have been learnt and per now all international core crimes have been legislated and the judicial system

¹³⁶ X "ICTR IN BRIEF" available at <https://unictr.irmct.org/en/tribunal#:~:text=With%20its%2> accessed March 10 2026

¹³⁷ ICTR, *supra note* 132, p. 28.

¹³⁸ J.B. MUTANGANA, *supra note* 128, p.4.

of Rwanda has been reformed, so that it can cope with the prosecution and repression of international crimes. Hence, this should be the lesson to the rest of the world where States have not yet complied with their international obligations to put in place legal measures aimed at enabling the effective domestic application of international criminal law¹³⁹

3.2.2 The Hybrid Accountability Model of the Special Court for Sierra Leone

Like Liberia, the Sierra Leone's brutal civil war (1991–2002) bequeathed a dark history of mass atrocities, war crimes, crimes against humanity, and systematic gender-based violence. As a means of prosecuting perpetrators for war crimes and crimes against humanity, in 2000, the Sierra Leonean government made a formal request to the U.N Security Council requesting support for the establishment of the Special Court of Sierra Leone. Based on the request, in August 2000, a U.N resolution 1315 was adopted thereby establishing the Special Court of Sierra Leone (SCSL) in 2002. The court was hybrid in nature, featuring both local and international elements while attempting to account for some of the experiences of the ad hoc International Criminal Tribunals for the former Yugoslavia and Rwanda (ICTY/ICTR).¹⁴⁰

The SCSL's mandate was to prosecute those bearing the greatest responsibility for violations of international humanitarian law and Sierra Leonean law committed since 1996. As a mixed tribunal, incorporating both international and national elements were essential, as it generated high expectations within the international community. The SCSL was generally deemed to herald a new model or benchmark for the assessment of future ad hoc international criminal courts.¹⁴¹

The Special Court also had the power to prosecute persons who bear the greatest individual criminal responsibility including those leaders who, in conducting such crimes, have threatened the establishment of and implementation of the peace process in Sierra Leone. Crimes covered by its Statute included Crimes Against Humanity, violation of the Geneva Conventions, other serious violations of international humanitarian law, and crimes under Sierra Leonean domestic law. These crimes include murder, extermination, enslavement, torture, rape, sexual slavery, forced

¹³⁹ N. Dieudonne, *supra* note 126, p.4

¹⁴⁰ T. Marah “*The international criminal justice mechanisms, Sierra Leone’s post-conflict accountability*” *Journal of Governance and Public Administration*, 2025, p. 2.

¹⁴¹ C. Jalloh, *supra* note 109, p.3.

prostitution and sexual violence, and persecution on the basis of politics, race, ethnicity, or religion.¹⁴²

One of the most famous cases the tribunal had was the trial of Charles Taylor, former president of Liberia, who was tried and convicted on 11 charges arising from war crimes, crimes against humanity, and other serious violations of international humanitarian law. On April 26, 2012 Special Court for Sierra Leone (SCSL) judges ruled that Taylor was guilty of aiding and abetting in all 11 charges, including murder, rape, and pillage.¹⁴³

The court was established in an international effort to end impunity for grave crimes. It was a court of many firsts, it was the first court to be established in the country where the crimes took place, the first hybrid court where international and national judges and personnel worked together; the first international court to be funded solely on voluntary contributions from interested states, the first to indict a sitting African head of state, and the first to convict individuals for the recruitment and use of child soldiers and for the crime of forced marriage.

So similarly, a hybrid court like the special court of Sierra Leone that was recommended by the Liberia TRC could ensure that Liberia prosecute serious crimes, while benefiting from international expertise and technical support, especially in cases where domestic capacity is still limited. And strengthening mutual legal assistance will make such domestication feasible.

In essence, many other post-conflict African nations have also incorporated core international crimes into their domestic law particularly following the end of armed conflicts, civil war or mass atrocities. Some through international supports established an extraordinary tribunal and ad hoc court for investigating, prosecuting and sentencing perpetrators of international crimes. As already discussed in the case of Rwanda and Sierra Leone. Other African States like Uganda enacted an international criminal core act in 2010 incorporating the Rome Statute into their domestic laws and created an international crimes division within its High court.¹⁴⁴

¹⁴² X “Hybrid Justice” available at <https://hybridjustice.com/special-court-for-sierra-leone/#> accessed , March 12, 2026

¹⁴³ Opening society Justice initiative, “*The Trial of Charles Taylor by the Special Court for Sierra Leone: the Appeal Judgment*” Briefing Paper, 2013, p.2.

¹⁴⁴ International Criminal Court Act of Uganda, 2010

The democratic Republic of Congo court also adopted an Implementing legislation incorporating international crimes. A move which saw the country military court prosecuting war crimes domestically. The Congolese legislature promulgated Law 24/2002 of 18 November 2002 listing under the same military justice system the adjudication of war crimes, genocide and crimes against humanity.¹⁴⁵

Until recently, this law, which effectively transposes the Rome Statute into the military justice system, has been applied by the military tribunals in their efforts to prosecute international crimes committed in the territory of the DRC.¹⁴⁶ In 2015 it was amended thereby allowing Congolese courts to investigate, prosecute and adjudicate war crimes, crimes against humanity and genocide committed in the DRC. It was adopted unanimously by the National Assembly of the DRC on 2 June 2015, and it contains provisions strengthening cooperation with the ICC.¹⁴⁷

The experienced of Rwanda, Sierra Leone and other post-conflict nations that have domesticated international crimes offer important efforts for Liberia's efforts towards domesticating international crimes. Legislative reforms like the incorporation of international crimes into the Rwanda penal law, institutional designs like the special court for Sierra Leone and the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda, capacity buildings and international corporations are essential lessons for Liberia. So comparatively, Liberia can draw lessons from these post-conflict African States who have demonstrated the integration of international crimes through legislative reforms, and through the enactment of an international criminal crimes act.

¹⁴⁵ Law 24/2002 of 18 November 2002 concerning Military penal code of the Democratic Republic of Congo.

¹⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁴⁷ Law 15/022 of 31 December 2015, amending the Congolese Criminal Code and the Code of Criminal Procedure.

GENERAL CONCLUSION

This general conclusion is composed by conclusion and recommendations.

1. Conclusion

The culture of impunity has for a long time serve as a barrier to many legal systems around the world, particularly in the African region. The domestication of international crimes under the Liberian Criminal Law remains an ongoing challenge. Despite Liberia practice of a dualist legal system, and its ratification of key international legal instruments like the Rome Statute. This study has examined the domestication of international crimes under the Liberian criminal law by analyzing applicable international legal instruments, identifying key domestic challenges and proposing mechanism for reforms through both internal means and comparative insights.

Chapter one established the broader conceptual frameworks and general consideration governing the domestication of international crimes. It demonstrated that the incorporation of international criminal law into domestic system is significant for the effective functioning of the global accountability reigme. In particurlaly, the principle of complementarity under the Rome Statute of the international criminal court places an obligation on national jurisdiction to investigate and prosecute international crimes. This purposefully underscore the importance of domestic legal systems to ensure accountability for serious crimes like genocide, war crimes, and crimes against humanity. It further explored the theoretical foundation governing the incorporation of international crimes into domestic law, by highlighting the relationship between international and domestic law and that for dualist system like Liberia, legislative incorporation is a precondition for the enforcement of international obligation at the national level.

Building on this Chapter, Chapter Two critically examined the challenges hindering the domestication of international crimes under the Liberian criminal law. It analyzed that these challenges are both structural and institutional. Legally, the absence of an explicit provision criminalizing international crimes within Liberia criminal law frameworks represents a fundamental barrier to the domestication of international crimes within Liberia. This legislative gap is compounded by a broader constitutional constraint, particularly the principle of *nullum crimen sine lege* and the prohibition of *ex post facto* laws which also present a significant obstacle to the domestication of international crimes, especially in the absence of legislative incorporation.

Institutionally, the study found that Liberia lacks the capacity to investigate and prosecute international crimes. Limitation in judicial and prosecutorial expertise, weak and limited judicial capacity, including inadequate investigative mechanisms collectively undermines the effectiveness of the criminal justice system. Furthermore, the study analyzed how other constraints have contributed to delays in implementing key reforms, like the establishment of an extraordinary criminal court, as recommended by the Liberia Truth and Reconciliation Commission.

Chapter three finally focused on the necessary mechanisms for overcoming these challenges and strengthening the domestication of international crimes in Liberia. It emphasized that effective domestication requires a holistic approach that combine legislative reforms, institutional strengthening and practical enforcement mechanisms. These included, the enactment of a comprehensive international crimes act, reform of the penal law, and the establishment of a specialized or hybrid court as recommended by the TRC, that would be capable of handling crimes of both international and national elements. In addition, the study underscores the importance of strengthening investigative mechanism through the establishment of specialize international crimes unit, witness and victim protection mechanisms as means to ensure credible and effective prosecution.

Comparative analysis of both Rwanda and Sierra Leone provided valuable practical insights by illustrating how legal reforms, hybrid judicial mechanism, capacity building and international supports can collectively facilitate accountability for international crimes. This comparative work demonstrated that domestication of international crimes require sustained commitment and coordination among multiple actors.

Overall, this study has proven that the domestication of international crimes in Liberia is both a legal and institutional project that requires a deliberate legislative action. Strengthening institutional capacity and international cooperation. Achieving these objectives is critical not only for fulfilling international legal obligations but also for addressing the legacy of past atrocities, promoting accountability, and strengthening the rule of law.

2. Recommendations

In views of these findings, the following recommendations are proposed to these concern institutions and groups as means of enhancing the quest for the domestication of international crimes.

a.To the Ministry of Justice of Liberia (MOJ)

I kindly recommend that you draft an enabling legislation either through a legal reform that incorporates international crimes (war crimes, crimes against humanity and Genocide) under the Liberia penal law. Strengthen prosecutorial and Investigative capacity by creating specialize units trained in international crimes. And that you also engage in public legal education to prepare the public for the implications of prosecutions under international law.

b.To the Parliament of Liberia

Recommend that you also enact a comprehensive legislation to domesticate international crimes, either through reforms or the enactment of an international crimes act that would include clear definitions and penalties of these crimes. Amend constitutional and statutory provisions where necessary to address such as retroactive prosecution limitations while respecting fundamental principles of legality.

And also ensure budgetary and institutional support to the establishment of the war and economic crimes court, investigative units, and other mechanisms necessary for the enforcement of international crimes.

c. To Civil Society Organizations in Liberia

Conduct an advocacy campaign urging the government and parliament to act on legal reforms and the establishment of a hybrid court. Partner with international organization to amplify the call for justice and provide technical support for capacity building initiatives. And also monitor compliance and implementation of reforms and provide recommendations to strengthen accountability measures.

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